

Some Reactions of 2-Diazoindan-1-one

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Alcoholic solutions of 2-diazoindan-1-one with dilute sulphuric acid does not provide the expected 2-hydroxyindan-1-one, but affords 2-alkoxyindan-1-ones. Thus, 2-ethoxy-, 2-methoxy-, and 2-benzyloxy-indan-1-one are formed when appropriate alcohols are used as solvents. 2-Chloro-, 2-bromo-, 2-hydroxy-, and 2-acetoxy-indan-1-one and 2, 2'-bis-inden-1-one have been directly prepared from 2-diazoindan-1-one. Two 2, 4-dinitrophenylhydrazones of 2-bromoindan-1-one, believed to be geometrical isomers, have been isolated.

Recent studies by the present authors on some reactions of 2-diazoindan-1-one (I), prepared earlier by Cava *et al.*¹, led to unexpected but interesting results. Ishiwara² and later Schopf and Kuhne³ reported the preparation of 2-hydroxyindan-1-one (II) by transformation of 2-bromoindan-1-one (III) to 2-acetoxyindan-1-one (IV) and subsequent hydrolysis. Since in aqueous alcoholic solution diazoketones are normally decomposed by dilute sulphuric acid to furnish hydroxymethylketones⁴, we adopted this procedure with a view to synthesising the hydroxyketone (II) directly from the diazoketone (I). Treatment of an aqueous ethanolic solution of (I) with dilute sulphuric acid did not, however, yield the expected ketol (II) (lit.² m.p. 38-40°), but afforded a colorless crystalline product (A), m.p. 70-71°. It failed to respond to the usual tests of an α -ketol, but formed a crystalline 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (DNP), m.p. 223-24°. Again, when the sulphuric acid-catalysed reaction of the diazoketone (I) was conducted in aqueous methanolic solution, a colorless oil (B), b.p. 89°/0.5 mm, was obtained. It behaved typically like the preceding compound (A) and formed a crystalline DNP, m.p. 248° (decomp.). Similarly with benzyl alcohol, a liquid (C), b.p. 65-66°/2 mm, was obtained. Its DNP melted at 279°.

Isolation of the three products, (A), (B) and (C), when different alcohols were used as solvents, led us to conclude that the reaction did not take the normal course and the solvent probably took part in the reaction. It was postulated that in acid medium (I) reacted with alcohols to afford 2-alkoxyindan-1-ones. Subsequent studies have shown that such a course of reaction did take place since the products (A), (B), and (C) have been identified as the ethers (VI), (VII), and (VIII) respectively. The evidence in favour of the structural assignment is presented below.

1. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 2257.

2. *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1924, **ii**, 108, 194.

3. *Ber.*, 1950, **83**, 390.

4. "Newer Methods of Preparative Organic Chemistry", Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York 1948, pp. 540, 567.

(I)

(II): R=OH.

(III): R=Br.

(IV): R=OAc.

(V): R = Cl.

(VI): R=OEt.

(VII): R=OMe.

(VIII): R=OCH₂Ph.

Treatment of (I) with ethanol in presence of boron trifluoride etherate, under conditions used by Mateos *et al.*⁵ for replacement of diazo group by alkoxy groups in a steroid diazoketone, afforded 2-ethoxyindan-1-one (VI), m.p. 70-71°, which formed a DNP, m.p. 223-24°. These melting points coincide with those of (A) and its DNP respectively. Identity of (A) with (VI) was established by the mixed m.p. determination of the two and their DNPs. When ethanol was replaced by benzyl alcohol in the above boron trifluoride-catalysed reaction, 2-benzyloxyindan-1-one (VIII), b.p. 70°/2.5 mm, was obtained. It formed a DNP (m.p. 279°), m.p. of which was not depressed when admixed with the specimen of C-DNP. Thus, the identity of (C) with (VIII) was substantiated.

Again, formulation of (B) as (VII) was confirmed since the m.p. 248° (decomp.) of B-DNP was undepressed on admixture with an authentic specimen of 2-methoxyindan-1-one DNP, m.p. 248° (decomp.), prepared according to Ramirez and Kirby⁶ by methanolysis of 2-bromoindan-1-one DNP.

During the course of our repetition of the work of Ramirez and Kirby⁶, who record the preparation of only *one* 2-bromoindan-1-one DNP, m.p. 205-206°, some interesting observations have been made. Under two sets of experimental conditions, *two* DNPs of 2-bromoindan-1-one⁷ (III) have been isolated. When ethylene glycol dimethyl ether (Diglyme) was used according to the method prescribed by Shine⁸ for the preparation of DNPs, III-DNP was readily obtained, which melted at 217-18°, whereas the use of Brady's reagent⁹, as recommended by Ramirez and Kirby⁶, furnished the DNP, m.p. 206-207° (lit.⁶ m.p. 205-206°). The isolation of *two* DNPs indicates their geometrical isomerism, (IX) and (X). This is supported by the following observations. The mixture of the isomers melted over a range 202-214° and these were interconvertible. When refluxed in chloroform solution with a trace of HCl (conc). for 3 hr., the higher-melting DNP isomerised to the lower-melting product, but the latter remained unchanged under the similar reaction condition. Isomerisation of the lower to the higher melting DNP was, however, effected by crystallisation from dioxane. Ramirez and Kirby⁶ have shown that the bromine atom in 2-bromoindan-1-one DNP is labile since, on methanolysis, it is replaced by methoxyl group to produce VII-DNP; this we have confirmed in the case of the DNP, m.p. 206-207°, which when refluxed in methanol for 6 hr. is converted into VII-DNP. But the isomeric DNP, m.p. 217-18°, was recovered unchanged after a similar treatment. The bromine atom in this instance is not displaced, presumably due to steric hindrance, and this may be realised if the *anti* structure (X) is assigned

5. *Tetrahedron*, 1963, 19, 1051.

6. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 8026.

7. Johnson and Shelberg, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 1745.

8. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1958, 24, 252.

9. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 757.

to the DNP, m.p. 217-18°. Consequently, it follows that the reactive DNP isomer, m.p. 206-207°, has the *syn* structure (IX) where such steric retardation is absent. We are, however, unable to confirm the proposed structural assignment as both the isomers exhibit identical absorption spectra in the UV and IR regions.

Since the acid-catalysed reaction of the diazoketone (I) with alcohols afforded 2-alkoxyindan-1-ones, it is reasonable to conclude that an ion-pair process, as suggested by Krimse¹⁰ in the substitution reactions of aliphatic diazonium groups, is involved in these instances. The diazoketone (I) is protonated by alcohols in acid medium to form primarily diazonium alkoxide ion pairs from which ethers (VI, VII, VIII) are obtained. The formation of the ethers indicates an anion exchange at the stage of the diazonium ion, and not at the carbonium-ion stage; the results are best explained by partial SN2-character of the substitution¹⁰.

Other reactions of (I) studied are in conformity with the usual behaviour of diazoketones. In aqueous tetrahydrofuran with dilute sulphuric acid, (I) afforded the expected 2-hydroxyindan-1-one (II) as a viscous oil, b.p. 152°/2 mm (lit⁸, m.p. 38-40°). It was characterised according to the literature procedure⁸ by its periodate oxidation to *o*-carboxyphenylacetaldehyde. When the ketone (I) was allowed to react with acetic acid in presence of cuprous oxide, 2-acetoxyindan-1-one (IV) was obtained and from this, the oxime derivative was prepared. Both the compounds have physical constants in agreement with the recorded values⁸. The diazoketone (I) with HCl furnished 2-chloroindan-1-one¹¹ (V) which

10. *Angew. Chem. internat. Ed.*, 1964, 3, (2), 146.

11. Courtot *et al.*, *Compt. rend.*, 1928, 186, 371.

formed a DNP, m.p. 205° (lit.¹¹ m.p. 205°). Hydrobromic acid treatment of (I) yielded the 2-bromo analogue (III)⁷; its DNP had m.p. 206-207° (lit.⁶ m.p. 205-206°).

A benzene solution of 2-diazoindan-1-one (I) in presence of cuprous oxide furnished 2,2'-bis-indan-1-one (XII), formed by the elimination of nitrogen and dimerisation of the resulting ketocarbene intermediate (XI).

*EXPERIMENTAL

2-Ethoxyindan-1-one (VI): Method (a).—To a solution of 2-diazoindan-1-one¹ (2.0 g.) in ethanol (15 ml) and water (2 ml) was added 1*N*-H₂SO₄ (2 ml). When evolution of nitrogen had subsided, the solution was heated on a water bath for 15 min. and left overnight at the room temperature. Most of the ethanol was then distilled, the residual solution diluted with water to turbidity, and cooled when a white solid separated. It was collected, dried, and distilled under reduced pressure. The distillate (b.p. 107-108°/3.5 mm) soon solidified to a colorless crystalline mass which was recrystallised from aqueous methanol (ice chest) to yield (VI) as needles (1.6 g.); m.p. 70-71°, with previous sintering at 62°. (Found: C, 74.7; H, 6.6. C₁₁H₁₂O₂ requires C, 75.0; H, 6.8%).

Its DNP, prepared according to Shine's method⁸, was crystallised from Diglyme as orange rectangular plates, m.p. 223-24°. (Found: N, 15.5. C₁₇H₁₆O₅N₄ requires N, 15.7%).

Method (b).—Adopting the procedure of Mateos *et al.*⁵, a solution of (I) (2 g.) in anhydrous ethanol (50 ml) was treated at the room temperature with boron trifluoride etherate (4.5 ml) and refluxed on a water bath for 4 hr. Most of the ethanol was distilled from the reaction mixture; water (150 ml) was added to turbidity and it was kept in a frigidiare overnight when almost colorless needles separated. These were collected and purified as above to afford (VI, 1.8 g.); m.p. and mixed m.p. 70-71°. Its DNP, prepared as above, had m.p. and mixed m.p. 223-24°.

2-Benzoyloxyindan-1-one (VIII): Method (a).—1*N*-H₂SO₄ (4 ml) was added dropwise with stirring to a solution of (I) (5 g.) in benzyl alcohol (25 ml) and the mixture left overnight at the room temperature. The unchanged benzyl alcohol was removed by steam distillation and the aqueous residue extracted with ether. The dried (Na₂SO₄) extract on evaporation left an oily residue which was distilled in *vacuo* to yield pure (VIII) as a colorless oil (4 g.), b.p. 65-66°/2 mm. (Found: C, 80.4; H, 5.5. C₁₆H₁₄O₂ requires C, 80.6; H, 5.8%).

Its DNP, prepared by Shine's method⁸, was crystallised from chloroform as red, irregular plates, m.p. 279°. (Found: N, 13.0. C₂₂H₁₈O₅N₄ requires N, 13.3%).

Method (b).—A solution of (I) (2 g.) in freshly distilled benzyl alcohol (15 ml) was treated at the room temperature with boron trifluoride etherate (4.5 ml) and left overnight.

*All melting points are uncorrected.

After heating on a water bath for 1 hr., the mixture was poured into cold water (250 ml) and worked up as in method (a) to furnish (VIII) as a colorless liquid (1.5 g.), b.p. 70°/2.5 mm. It afforded the DNP; m.p. and mixed m.p. 279°.

2-Methoxyindan-1-one (VII).—To a cooled solution of (I) (5 g.) in methanol (25 ml) and water (2 ml) 1*N*-H₂SO₄ (2 ml) was added. After ½ hr. it was heated on a water bath for 10 min. and left overnight. Most of the methanol was next distilled, the oily residue diluted with water (50 ml), and ether-extracted. The extract was washed with water and dried (Na₂SO₄). Removal of the solvent left an oil which on distillation in *vacuo* yielded (VII) as a colorless oil (3 g.), b.p. 89°/0.5 mm, 120°/5mm. (Found: C, 73.8; H, 5.9. C₁₀H₁₀O₂ requires C, 74.07; H, 6.1%).

The DNP, prepared by Shine's method⁸, was crystallised from Diglyme as red, rhombic plates, m.p. 248° (decomp.). (Found: N, 16.0. Calc. for C₁₆H₁₄O₃N₄: N, 16.3%).

The m.p. was not depressed when admixed with an authentic specimen of 2-methoxyindan-1-one DNP, prepared according to Ramirez and Kirby⁶.

2-Bromoindan-1-one DNP, m.p. 217-18° (X).—Adopting the method of Shine⁸, 2-bromoindan-1-one⁷ afforded the DNP (X) which was crystallised from dioxane to afford orange, rectangular flakes, m.p. 217-18°. (Found: N, 14.1; Br, 20.2. Calc. for C₁₅H₁₁O₄N₄ Br: N, 14.3; Br, 20.5%). $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{chl}}$ 390 m μ (ϵ , 30190).

2-Bromoindan-1-one DNP, m.p. 206-207° (IX).—2-Bromoindan-1-one⁷ furnished the DNP (IX) when Brady's reagent⁹ was used in accordance with the method of Ramirez and Kirby⁶. It was crystallised from chloroform-ethyl acetate as orange, prismatic needles, m.p. 206-207°. $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{chl}}$ 390 m μ (ϵ , 30190). (lit⁶, m.p. 205-206° and $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{chl}}$ 387 m μ (ϵ , 30200). A mixture of the two DNPs melted at 202-14°.

Isomerisation of the DNP (X).—A solution of (X) (500 mg.) in chloroform (25 ml) was treated with a few drops of HCl (conc.) and refluxed for 3 hr. On removal of the solvent, the residue was crystallised from chloroform-ethyl acetate to yield orange needles, m.p. 206-207°, undepressed on admixture with (IX).

Isomerisation of the DNP (IX).—Crystallisation of the DNP (IX) from dioxane yielded orange needles, m.p. 217-18°, undepressed when admixed with (X).

A solution of the DNP (IX, 500 mg.) in chloroform (25 ml) was treated with a few drops of HCl (conc.) and refluxed for 3 hr. On working up, unchanged material was recovered.

Methanolysis of the DNPs (IX) and (X)

1. *With (IX)*.—The DNP (IX, 350 mg.) was refluxed with methanol (350 ml) for a period of 6 hr. The halogen-free product, isolated from the reaction solution, on crystallisation from dioxane afforded 2-methoxyindan-1-one DNP as orange crystals, m.p. 248° (decomp.) [lit⁶, m.p. 248° (decomp.)], undepressed on admixture with VII-DNP.

2. *With (X)*.—A solution of the DNP (X, 350 mg.) in methanol (350 ml) was refluxed for 6 hr.; only unchanged material was recovered which gave positive Bilestein test.

2-Hydroxyindan-1-one (II).—1*N*-H₂SO₄ (3 ml) was added dropwise to a stirred solution of (I) (2g.) in THF (15 ml) and water (2 ml). After $\frac{1}{2}$ hr., when the evolution of nitrogen had subsided, it was heated on a water bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. On removal of THF, the oily liquid separating from the reaction mixture was extracted with ether. The extract was washed with 5% aq. NaHCO₃ and water and dried (Na₂SO₄). Evaporation of the ether left a tan, oily residue which was distilled under reduced pressure to furnish (II) as a colorless, viscous liquid (0.75 g.); b.p. 152°/2mm (lit³. m.p. 38-40°). On oxidation with periodic acid, according to the literature method³, it afforded *o*-carboxyphenylacetaldehyde which was crystallised from ethyl acetate-petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) as colorless needles, m.p. 97-98° (lit³ m.p. 97-98°).

2-Acetoxyindan-1-one (IV).—The diazoketone (I) (750 mg.) in glacial acetic acid (35 ml) was treated with cuprous oxide (75 mg.) and the mixture was set aside at the room temperature. Next day it was filtered, the filtrate was poured into water (200 ml), and extracted with ether. The extract was washed with 5% aq. NaHCO₃ and water and dried (Na₂SO₄). On evaporation of the solvent, an oily residue was obtained which was distilled under reduced pressure to afford (IV) (500 mg.) as a colorless liquid; b.p. 140°/2 mm (lit³. b.p. 137°/1 mm). It was characterised by preparing its oxime, m.p. 142° (lit³. m.p. 142°).

2-Chloroindan-1-one (V).—Adopting the procedure of Mateos *et al*⁵, a solution of the diazoketone (I) (500 mg.) in ether (25 ml) was cooled to 5° and treated under stirring with HCl (0.3 ml, *d* 1.16). After 10 min., the ethereal layer was successively washed with water (100 ml), 50% aq. NaHCO₃, and water. The dried extract (Na₂SO₄) on evaporation yielded (V, 400 mg.) as an oil (lit¹¹. m.p. 38-39°). Using Shine's method⁸, its DNP was obtained as scarlet prisms, m.p. 205° (lit¹¹. m.p. 205°).

2-Bromoindan-1-one (III) was prepared by following the above method for the preparation of (V). Thus from (I) (500 mg.) in ether (25 ml) and saturated aqueous solution of HBr (4 ml.), (III) (410 mg.) was obtained as a colorless liquid (lit⁷. m.p. 36-37°). It afforded two DNPs: (i) m.p. 217-18°, prepared according to Shine's method⁸; the m.p. was undepressed on admixture with (X); (ii) m.p. 206-207° (lit⁶. m.p. 205-206°), prepared by using Brady's reagent⁹. The m.p. was undepressed on admixture with (IX).

2,2'-Bis-indan-1-one(XII).—A mixture of cuprous oxide (50 mg.) and the diazoketone (I) (500 mg.) in benzene (50 ml) was allowed to stand overnight at the room temperature. It was refluxed for 30 min., diluted with benzene (100ml.), filtered, and the filtrate washed with water and dried (Na₂SO₄). Evaporation of the solvent left a brown solid which was crystallised from a large volume of boiling glacial acetic acid to afford (XII) as yellow, rectangular prisms (30 mg.), m.p. 236° (decomp.). It developed an orange colour with H₂SO₄ (conc.). (Found: C, 79.70; H, 4.20. C₁₈H₁₄O₂ requires C, 80.07; H, 4.60%).